

Unravelling the Threads of Unemployment in India: A Comprehensive Analysis

George Varghese and Leena Vora

ABSTRACT

Human capital is important for social and industrial innovation. Unemployment arises when a substantial portion of the population, capable and willing to work, is unable to find employment. This paper aims to deeply understand the causes and consequences of unemployment in India, using literature published between 2016 to 2023 as a secondary source of data. The study concluded that the skill mismatch and lack of quality educational opportunities are the main causes of unemployment in India. The government has taken several policy measures and initiated developmental programs like Viksit Bharat 2047 to mitigate India's unemployment. Tackling unemployment needs a comprehensive strategy encompassing education, industry, labor market enhancements, supportive economic policies, fostering remote work options, stimulating entrepreneurship to harness the demographic dividend of India, and initiating mental health-focused employment programs for the successful re-integration of the unemployed into the work pool.

Keywords: Human capital, Unemployment, India, Holistic approach, Viksit Bharat 2047, Demographic Dividend.

INTRODUCTION

Human resources are vital for market success. They bring diverse skills and innovations and influence workforce productivity. A skilled workforce provides a strategic advantage, shaping organizational culture and fostering adaptability to market changes. Human resources play a pivotal role in boosting social and industrial improvement. The labor force comprises employed and unemployed individuals who are able and interested in working. Unemployment is the scenario in which a substantial portion of the population, is willing and able to work, but find themselves without employment. Unemployment is

a scenario in which individuals who are capable of working actively seek work but are unable to find it.

As a developing economy, in India, unemployment differs from that in developed countries, affecting both rural and urban areas. High population growth boosts job demand, but available jobs fall short. Low education and skills, along with inadequate government support, poor infrastructure, and insufficient investment in manufacturing, exacerbate unemployment. Given India's developing status, with a majority residing in rural areas, there is a heavy reliance on irregular informal jobs. The primary sector faces challenges such as low productivity and limited alternatives for agricultural workers, hindering their transition to the industrial or services sector Nair (2020). Dwivedi (2019) A high level of unemployment is associated with a lower Gross Domestic Product (GDP) for the economy which means that the economy is not efficient. This leads to reduced production and income levels. Additionally, those who are unemployed face financial constraints to buy goods. Consecutively, it contributes to low spending and output in the economy.

Human capital and economic growth are closely linked. However, unemployment hampers economic growth and expansion, leading to increased poverty due to insufficient or no income. The present study was conducted to analyze the unemployment issue in India.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Pavithra (2022) stated that due to the migration of people from rural to urban regions job requirements in urban areas increase leading to a high rate of unemployment. Majumdar and Mukherjee (2018) found that the skills or training received by youth in India are inadequate. There is a mismatch between supply and demand in the labor market of India. High youth unemployment, especially among the educated, can escalate social tension and unrest, turning the demographic dividend into a nightmare. Therefore, India faces a critical issue of the highly educated being unemployed, with concerns about the employability of youth. Rathore (2019) found out that widespread unemployment stems from educated youth prioritizing 'white-collar jobs' and facing a lack of awareness and vocational guidance. Nair (2020) discussed that rapid population growth, especially among the youth, has outpaced job creation, resulting in widespread unemployment. Limited education and literacy exacerbate the problem. Additionally, inflation without a proportional increase in goods and services reduces real income. The surplus labor supply over demand depresses wages, leading to dissatisfaction and higher unemployment. Seasonal employment in agriculture further compounds job scarcity, pushing many into the informal sector with low and irregular wages.

Nagar (2021) mentioned that human capital formation is key to turning a large population into an asset, requiring investment in skills and education. While physical capital is vital for growth, its effectiveness depends on human capital. India's educational attainment has improved, but secondary and tertiary education rates are still low. Srivastav and Singh (2022) stated that skill mismatch in the Indian labor market has increased over time, which is a major concern. The primary reason is the increase in human capital due to policy efforts and the lack of demand for the workforce, resulting in underutilization of this human capital. Premee and Pal (2022) discussed that despite having abundant natural resources, India faces significant rural unemployment. The issue stems not from a lack of resources but from demographic challenges and the inability to effectively utilize unskilled labor in labor-intensive industries. Globalization and rapid urbanization are further altering the landscape of rural employment.

Dwivedi (2019) explained that jobless individuals indulge in unlawful or self-destruction practices leading to problems for the human resources of the country. When people are jobless for a longer period, they lose work abilities and become less employable in the future. Unemployment is a key economic indicator, reflecting the potential of skilled individuals to find work. A higher rate signals less productive economic growth. As per the India Employment Report 2024, unemployment is predominantly a challenge among Indian youth, as unemployed youth formed 82.9% of the total unemployed population in 2022. This is a grave scenario, especially when 27% of India's population constitute the youth. Silva et al., (2016) found that the inclusion of internships in higher education is negatively related to unemployment levels. The 2020 National Education Policy, announced internship schemes from Class 6 onwards and issued guidelines for institutions to offer degree programs with mandatory internships. Kamboj (2023) stated that despite being a major global player with a young population and democracy, India has considerable untapped potential. Unemployment reduces income directly, as jobs provide wages, and losing a job means lower available income for individuals.

OBJECTIVES

Unemployment stands as a significant challenge worldwide, bringing about societal stigma for individuals and resulting in the wastage of human potential. In India it is a major and ongoing issue, impacting the economy across various sectors. It has been affecting both rural and urban areas persistently. The present study is focused on the problem of unemployment in India and interprets different factors, causes, and consequences of unemployment. The paper deliberates on the issue faced by the economy due to the high unemployment rate.

METHODOLOGY

The present study is based on secondary data collected from different research papers, and reports. For this Elsevier, ScienceDirect, and other published sources were used. After a review of 25 published literature, 12 papers, 1 conference paper, and 1 report were included in the study. The words unemployment, India, causes, consequences, policies, human capital, demographic dividend and economy used in Google Scholar to search for appropriate literature. Duplication of the content was removed.

- Inclusion criteria: The academic papers from peer-reviewed journals and reports published in English language between 2016 to 2023.
- Exclusion criteria: The research material on unemployment published in languages other than English and studies published before 2016.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

High unemployment can restrain the economic growth of a country by reducing overall productivity and consumption. When a significant portion of the population is not working, the economy fails to achieve its full productive potential and income levels. The following studies focus on the causes and consequences of unemployment in India.

Table 1

Research papers and Reports included in the Study

S. No.	Author/s	Source	Year of publication	DOI/URL
1.	Kamboj, R.	International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts	2023	https://www.ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT2305143.pdf
2.	Zala et al.	Conference: Unemployment Analysis	2023	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369890680_A_STUDY_ON_UNEMPLOYMENT_IN_INDIA
3.	Behera and Gaur	International Center for Research and Resources Development	2022	https://search.crossref.org/?q=icrrd&from_ui=yes
4.	Chaturvedi, A.	International Journal of Advanced Research in Commerce, Management & Social Science	2022	https://www.inspirajournals.com/uploads/Issues/1292159930.pdf

S. No.	Author/s	Source	Year of publication	DOI/URL
5.	Khare, M.	Report	2022	https://whec2022.net/resources/
6.	Pavithra, B.	International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research	2022	https://www.ijfmr.com/papers/2023/4/4541.pdf
7.	Premi and Pal	International Journal of All Research Education and Scientific Methods	2022	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/370203697_Nature_and_Magnitude_of_Rural_Unemployment_in_India/download
8.	Ramteke, A.	International Journal of Innovative Research In Technology	2022	https://ijirt.org/master/publishedpaper/IJIRT156516_PAPER.pdf
9.	Srivastav and Sigh	ĀRTHIKĪ	2022	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358107174_Skill_Mismatch_in_Labour_Market_Evidence_from_Indian_States
10.	Vijayalakshmi, C.	International Journal Of Innovative Research In Technology	2022	https://ijirt.org/master/publishedpaper/IJIRT157309_PAPER.pdf
11.	Nagar, P.	International Journal of Basic and Applied Research	2021	https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3889259
12.	Nair, S.	International Review of Business and Economics	2020	https://doi.org/10.56902/IRBE.2020.4.2.49
13.	Dwivedi, M. C.	Global Journal of Progressive Education	2019	https://globusedujournal.in/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/GE-JJ12-Dwivedi.pdf
14.	Rathore, C.	Inspira- Journal of Modern Management & Entrepreneurship	2019	https://www.inspirajournals.com/uploads/Issues/1787608161.pdf
15.	Kapoor and Indapurkar	Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research	2019	https://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR1903E93.pdf
16.	Silva et al.	Higher Education	2016	http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10734-015-9903-9

While reviewing different studies, it was found that illiteracy, skill mismatch, changing job market, lack of resources in rural areas, and population growth are the main causes of unemployment in India. Chaturvedi (2022) mentioned in the study that an increase in population, illiteracy, inflation, and lack of full-time employment can lead to a high rate of unemployment. Zala et al., (2023) stated that in India, there is a mismatch between the skills employers need and job seekers' skills. Many industries seek highly skilled workers, but education and training systems have not kept up with the changing job market, leaving many positions unfilled. Additionally, automation and technological advancements have made many jobs redundant.

Kapoor and Indapurkar (2019) observed a gap between the theoretical and practical knowledge provided to Indian youth. Industry requires basic knowledge and the practical application of the same at work which is not being offered leading to a mismatch of skill and employment. Industries require both fundamental knowledge and its practical application, which is often lacking. As a result, workers are not equipped with market-ready skills. Khare (2022) found that institutions in India often fail to keep up with advancements in basic disciplines, knowledge, and technology. Outdated curriculum, institutional apathy, faculty resistance to change, and infrastructural issues contribute to employer dissatisfaction with graduates leading to educated unemployed. While discussing different problems faced by jobless people Dwivedi (2019) mentioned that unemployment leads to hopelessness, mental health problems, severe medical issues, and viciousness among jobless people.

Vijayalakshmi (2022) explained that unemployment increases government borrowing due to reduced production and consumption, and raises socio-economic costs as the unemployed class depends on the working class. Parida and Madheswaran (2023) mentioned that the Indian economy is facing a critical phase, with millions leaving agriculture annually, and non-farm sector job growth insufficient to absorb them. Educated youth unemployment is on the rise, with about 24 million unemployed. Kamboj (2023) stated that unemployment does not only affect unemployed people but also businesses and industries that rely on consumer spending.

CONCLUSION

Despite the young workforce, India is facing a significant issue of unemployment. The study concluded that both rural and urban areas face similar changes such as low skills, faulty education systems, overpopulation, and a gap between theoretical and practical knowledge. Unemployment in rural areas mainly occurs due to a lack of resources and education. Migration from rural to urban areas escalates unemployment. Unemployment not only affects an individual's physical and mental health but also harms the economy of

the country. The standard of living between the jobless and working class leads to social disparity which leads to illegal acts by the unemployed class. Although the Government has planned different policies and implemented many schemes for providing employment, those are not enough to provide job opportunities to all because the population is the major concern in India. Therefore, tackling unemployment requires a holistic approach involving education, labor market improvements, supportive economic policies, and the promotion of entrepreneurship.

IMPLICATIONS FOR SOCIAL POLICY AND ACTION

The present study highlights several causes of unemployment and their effect on the individuals and economic growth of India. To address these challenges, appropriate education and training programs aligning with the skills required for the jobs are needed. Government policies should focus on the creation of jobs for freshers and invest their potential in new industries. During recessions or problems like the COVID-19 pandemic, many people have lost their jobs. It is necessary to support individuals affected by job loss and provide them with other alternatives. Entrepreneurship can generate new opportunities. Promotion and encouragement of such opportunities are necessary for the full utilization of human resources. Entrepreneurship is crucial for a country's development, economic growth, and standard of living. During the adaptation of new technologies, training programs for upskilling are crucial Ramteke (2022). Understanding the structural issues within the urban and rural labor market can make it easier for businesses to hire and for people to find jobs. Addressing unemployment can improve overall productivity by ensuring that human resources can be utilized in a better way.

Employment is a key factor for poverty reduction. Therefore, addressing this problem helps improve the standard of living in society. Unemployment leads to social problems such as illegal or self-destruction practices by jobless people Dwivedi (2019). Reduction in unemployment will bring social stability and cohesion. The overall well-being of individuals is related to the work they do. Thus, focusing on unemployment can have a positive effect on public health. Similar to the measures taken by Japan such as job-oriented training Yamada (2017), Governments should aim to promote entrepreneurship through effective resource utilization to boost per capita income, exports, and employment opportunities.

A UNIQUE CONTRIBUTION TO THE EXISTING LITERATURE

India has the world's youngest population. However, a major part of the workforce struggles with the lack of quality education and skill development required for the job. We are unable to produce enough job opportunities. The demand for professionals in the labor

market is low. Due to this unemployment rate is high and the employability condition of the market is poor. So, the three most important aspects needed are Job Skilling, Youth skilling, and demand for skilled Workforce. Skill development broadens the chances of employment by improving and nurturing skills. By utilizing skilled human potential, a nation can become a productive economy. Training methods like practical knowledge, conflict resolution, personality development, and soft skills are very important for skill development. Youth Skilling benefits new employees to be ready for new technologies. It serves as a tool for improving effectiveness and enables individuals to perform more efficiently. A skilled workforce is necessary for the competitive and productive economy of a country (Behera and Gaur, 2022). Currently, skills training in India is majorly government-driven with meagre participation of industry. According to Silva et al., (2016), study programs such as internships help graduates enhance their employability. Work-based learning is a successful way to bridge the gap between theoretical and practical knowledge. Entrepreneurship is crucial for a country's development, economic growth, and standard of living Ramteke (2022). To nurture disruptive idea generation from budding entrepreneurs and transform them into successful businesses, India needs to invest more in R&D. Successful collaborations between education and industry coupled with increased R&D spending, will take India a long way in achieving its dream of Viksit Bharat in 2047.

SCOPE OF FUTURE RESEARCH

The present study was conducted in the Indian context. Future studies can include other developing countries. Also, different steps taken by developed countries to reduce unemployment can be discussed in detail. A study on comparison between unemployment trends and causes in rural and urban areas can be conducted in detail to tailor the policies accordingly. The effect of international migration on employment can also be studied. The long-term effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on employment patterns and the labor market in India can be investigated.

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ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Dr. George Varghese, *Senior Consultant Psychologist*, Oyster & Pearl Hospitals

Leena Vora, *Assistant Vice President*, V SOLVE India Pvt. Ltd.